

“Stock-taking” institutional support for Citizen Science in RPOs

The following questions serve Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) to describe the institutional support that can lead to a better and more effective engagement of citizens in research and innovation via citizen science.

Answering these questions is a reflection exercise:

- It helps to identify areas, where more support for citizen science can be implemented, and demonstrate those areas, where already first institutional support for citizen science is already in place.
- It supports describing the baseline of institutional support before developing a roadmap of activities that aim to trigger institutional change towards citizen science.
- It assists in monitoring and keeping track of changes by revisiting these questions on a regular (e.g. yearly) basis.

The stock-taking questions are structured along the four intervention areas defined in the Time4CS project:

1. Research
2. Education and Awareness
3. Support resources and infrastructure
4. Policy and Assessment

They contain open and closed questions, where open questions are especially important - so RPOs are invited to not necessarily get hooked on the concrete numbers. Numbers also have merit, of course, but it is also important to reflect in an open qualitative way on the current situation.

Institutions may not have the full set of support structures that are mentioned in this questionnaire in place yet. It is still recommended to keep them in and possibly reflect on them as they serve for later reference. You may want to draw a comparison with data collected after the implementation of the first activities that support citizen science.

Here is an overview of the four intervention areas and potential indicators in each of these areas.

Indicators for Institutional Changes to support citizen science in RPOs

Figure 1: Indicators for institutional change in TIME4CS (changes at organisational level in the blue, orange, yellow and green rectangles; changes on the individual level in the grey rectangle).

General info: Opportunities and barriers

Opportunities

What do you think are the most important opportunities and triggers to make citizen science an accepted research approach within your organisation?

Concerns and barriers

What are the key concerns/barriers that hinder citizen science becoming an accepted research approach within your organisations?

1. Intervention Area: Support resources and infrastructures

1.1. Strategic plans to support CS:

- Are there any official plans in your organisation on how to support citizen science?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?

1.2. Funding citizen science activities:

- Are there funding opportunities for citizen science in your country?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?
 - Has your organisation already made use of them?
- Does your organization benefit from international/European funding of citizen science?
 - If yes, could you please briefly describe it?
- Is there any other internal funding available for the active involvement of citizens in research?
 - If yes, could you please briefly describe it?

1.3. Tools and protocols:

- Does your organisation have access to tools and technical solutions that support the implementation of citizen science projects (e.g. tools for data collection)?
 - If yes, could you please describe them shortly?
- Does your organisation provide legal protocols tailored to national requirements and ethical committees?
 - If yes, could you please describe them?

2. Intervention Area: Education and Awareness

2.1 Internal capacity building:

- How high do you think is the awareness for citizen science among your research personnel?
- And what do you think about their expertise regarding citizen science methodologies (e.g. methodologies on how to engage citizens in research, deal with data privacy aspects, and assure data quality?)
- Does your organisation offer training and teaching sessions on citizen science for researchers, support staff, students, or post-graduates?
 - If yes, how many and could you briefly describe them or provide a link to the training descriptions if available?
- Does your organisation offer workshops, inspirational talks, and informal get-togethers related to citizen science for researchers, support staff, students, or post-graduates?
 - If yes, how many approximately per year and could you briefly describe them?

2.2. Communication & debate:

- Do you have communication channels and information material, which invites the general public to be involved in research projects (e.g. a section on the institutions' website)?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?
- Does your organisation offer dialogue/discussions on citizen science with the general public?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?

2.3. Citizen Science expertise/Governance:

- Is citizen science driven by individual persons (Citizen science champions) within your organisation who are interested in citizen science?
 - If yes, how many approximately? From which research field do they come?

- Is citizen science already part of some persons' job description? And do these persons provide guidance, information, and support to other employees?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
- Is there a dedicated unit or contact point for citizen science? Does it provide support for citizen science to others inside and/or outside of the organisation? Is this unit sustainably funded or dependent on project funding?

3. Intervention Area: Policy and Assessment

3.1. Strategy and policy documents:

- Is science communication and public engagement integrated in your institutional research strategy or institutional statements?
- Does your organisation have open science policies established?
Is citizen science considered part of the open science policy?
- Does your organisation have any other norms, regulations and policies in place or under development that specifically refer to citizen science?
 - If yes, can you briefly describe them?

3.2. Researchers' evaluation:

- Are science communication and public engagement considered in the evaluation schemes of researchers (= academic staff appraisal)?
- Is the active involvement of citizens in scientific projects (citizen science) considered in the evaluation schemes of researchers (= academic staff appraisal)?

3.3. Management:

- Does your organisation offer presentations on citizen science at the management level?
- Does your organisation have any citizen science champions at the management level?
- Are researchers being encouraged by management to pursue citizen science activities?

4. Intervention Area: Research

4.1. Citizen Science Projects/proposals/initiatives:

- Are there any citizen science projects/proposals/initiatives in your organisation?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Is there a description available of these projects to get more details on funding, disciplines, size, scope, role of citizens, etc. (e.g. a website)?
 - Are there any flagship citizen science projects/initiatives amongst them, e.g. with wide national/international visibility?

4.2. Publications:

- Are there any scientific publications related to citizen science within your organisation?
 - If yes, how many approximately?

4.3. Networks:

- Do you actively cooperate and/or network with organisations that are active in the citizen science field?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Could you briefly describe them, please (e.g. NGOs in the environmental field ...)?
- Does your organisation have representatives in national/european-wide/international committees related to Citizen Science (e.g. ECSA board ...)?
 - If yes, could you elaborate on their engagement, please?
- Is there a national citizen science organisation in your country? Are you a member of it?
- Is your institution a member of the ECSA?

Other aspects that might be relevant to consider:

- Are there any other aspects that you want to document because they influence the support for citizen science in your organisation?